

AI4

eOSC

WP5 Updated implementation plan and progress report

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Prepared by	Reviewed by	Approved by
I. Heredia (CSIC)	V. Kozlov (KIT) A. Heredia (CSIC) A. Constantini (INFN) M. Plociennik (PSNC)	Project Management Board

Issue	Date	Description	Author(s)
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable outlines an updated Roadmap for WP5 components during the second part of the AI4EOSC project (AI4EOSC 2nd Release). For context, we briefly discuss the current status in light of the concluded Roadmap of AI4EOSC 1, where most of the objectives were successfully completed. From there, we present a detailed implementation plan for the AI4EOSC 2nd Release, explaining how the different milestones in the Roadmap interact with each other. We conclude that the evolution of the components will successfully deliver all the features expected from the project.

1 - INTRODUCTION

In this document we offer an updated implementation plan for the second part of the project (AI4EOSC 2nd Release). This plan updates the one initially outlined in Deliverable 5.1 [\[D5.1\]](#).

This document is structured as follows.

In [Section 2](#), we review the main architectural changes in WP5 components employed during the first part of the project, and how this is reflected in the progress status of the overall WP5.

In [Section 3](#), we propose an updated implementation Roadmap for the AI4EOSC 2nd Release, as well as discussing the main changes with respect to the previous one.

Finally, in [Section 4](#), we provide the conclusion.

2 - PROGRESS REPORT IN WP5

2.1 - ARCHITECTURE UPDATES

This section briefly gives an overview of the architectural updates regarding WP5, to provide the context for the following sections, namely the current status and the updated Roadmap.

For a detailed account of the architecture updates, especially in the context of the overall project, please refer to Deliverable 3.3 [\[D3.3\]](#). It is worth noting that many of these architecture changes were already discussed in the Deliverable 5.2 [\[D5.2\]](#) (section: “Deviations from the original roadmap”).

The main changes in the architecture during the first part of the project were the following:

- the *Training API* and the *Exchange API* have been merged into a single component (the *Platform API*),
- Instead of an *Exchange Database* component we rely on a GitHub repository; instead of a dedicated *Training Database* we make use of the Nomad database,
- the Platform API has been integrated with the *Secrets Management System* (Vault) to manage the secrets from the deployments and the Federated Learning Tool,
- the AI4Compose component has been expanded to showcase its subcomponents: *Elyra* to create flows with Jupyter notebooks, *Node-RED* to create flows from OSCAR modules, and *FlowFuse* to manage Node-RED flows,
- the *Continuous Integration* and the *Continuous Integration Delivery & Deployment* have been merged into a single component,
- the *Model and data repository* and *Model code repositories* have been merged into a single component,
- a *User deployment* component has been created to group the different Nomad tasks that are performed at the job’s start: launching DEEPaaS, launching the Interactive Development Environment, syncing with our

Platform Storage (Nextcloud) and downloading an external dataset from an external repository (e.g. Zenodo).

- the architecture has been updated to reflect the *tighter integration with Zenodo*, both automatically pushing models to Zenodo and retrieving datasets from Zenodo,
- the MLOps component has been updated to include references to MLflow and the drift monitoring tools.

2.2 - STATUS OF AI4EOSC 1 IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

This section briefly revisits the Roadmap for the first release of the platform, AI4EOSC 1, first described in Deliverable 5.1 [D5.1], comparing it with the actual status of the WP5 components.

As the implementation evaluation status was already extensively discussed in Deliverable 5.2 [D5.2], we will include here, only for context, the Table 1 of that Deliverable. This Table evaluates the completion status at the end of AI4EOSC 1 phase for each of the items of the Roadmap for AI4EOSC 1.

For an in-depth review of the status of the components, please refer to Deliverable 5.2.

Table 1: Status of the roadmap for AI4EOSC 1. Color code: (●) for completed work, (●) for partially completed work, (●) for work that didn't need to be completed after reevaluation. The Table originally belongs to Deliverable 5.2 [D5.2], but is included here for context.

Component/Actions	Status + Description
AI4Compose / Design + Proof of Concept	● - The first prototype offers the ability to create graphical AI pipelines both in Elyra and Node-RED/FlowFuse, offering connectors with OSCAR to compose inference pipelines in a drag-and-drop approach.
Training API implementation	● - As a part of the Platform API (in production), trainings are deployed as Nomad jobs.
Training database + API integration	● - Upon careful reevaluation, the implementation of a training database was not deemed necessary.
Training API integration with the Workload Management System	● - As a part of the Platform API (in production), it has the ability to manage deployments of Nomad jobs.
AI4EOSC Dashboard + Training + Exchange	● - A first prototype is successfully running in production, with the ability of serving a catalogue of modules and tools (Exchange) as well as deploying them (Training).

Component/Actions	Status + Description
Exchange API implementation	● - As a part of the Platform API (in production), a diverse catalogue of modules and tools is served to the user.
Exchange database + AI integration	● - Upon careful reevaluation, the implementation of an exchange database was not deemed necessary at the time being.
New code repositories	● - The work of moving to new (unified) repositories has started but has not yet been completed.
New container registry	● - A new container registry has been created with Harbor, and Docker images are synced with Docker Hub.
Interactive Development Environment	● - We have successfully integrated VScode and JupyterLab in the same Interactive Development Environment, deployable from the AI4EOSC Dashboard.

3 - UPDATED IMPLEMENTATION PLAN FOR THE AI4EOSC 2ND RELEASE

3.1 - TIMELINE

Figure 1 provides a graphical timeline showing when the new features for WP5 components during the AI4EOSC 2nd Release (months: M19-M33) will be implemented. This timeline summarises the roadmap explained in [Section 3.2](#).

As this deliverable is due in M24, it is worth noting that some of the new features described in this section might already have been implemented (in the period M19-M24). For consistency, this deliverable will use the future tense for all the features (already implemented or not).

In addition to those features, each of the WP5 components will have maintenance effort allocated to them. That effort will take place all along the duration of the AI4EOSC 2nd Release and is not shown in the timeline, for clarity.

Figure 1: Timeline of actions for the second AI4EOSC release. Green cells indicate the time range from development to deployment. All components will still be maintained and improved after deployment, though not shown in the Table to avoid clutter. Month 33 indicates the time of the second release.

3.2 - ROADMAP

This section describes in detail the items featured in the timeline, [Figure 1](#).

3.2.1 - New code repositories

This action mainly involves WP6 but is listed here because its outcomes are profoundly guiding the development of many WP5 components.

During the AI4EOSC 1st Release, we intended to complete the migration to the new code repositories. Due to the complexity of the migration, this process will overflow a few months into the AI4EOSC 2nd Release.

The migration objectives are the following.

First, this migration is going to **unify code repos with docker repos**, providing a simpler experience for users and for developers. All those repos will be hosted from now on in the “ai4os-hub” GitHub organisation [\[ai4-modules\]](#).

Along with this unification, we will create a **new version of the metadata**, deprecating old fields (inherited from the DEEP Hybrid DataCloud project [\[deephdc\]](#)) and creating new fields that will enable us to push forward other components in WP5. Moreover, we will enable automated migration for these metadata, in order to provide a smooth transition for the use cases. For example, the creation of different customised keyword sections will enable the Dashboard to offer a better filtering experience to the users (filtering by AI framework, by AI task, etc). More information in [Section 3.2.8](#) and [Section 3.2.12](#).

Finally we completely redesigned the Continuous Integration by migrating to JePL v2 [\[jepl\]](#). From now on, the Continuous Integration tasks are a combination of user-defined tests and those determined on the side of the Platform. The latter enables us to easily implement common steps that will run for all modules, without having to modify the Pipeline of each single module, enforcing all the necessary quality checks and further integrations at a platform wide level. These common steps will include:

- improved Software Quality validation, including API testing.
- ability to push model releases to Zenodo automatically.
- automatic pushes to the Harbor Docker registry.
- automatic Pull Request creation in the module repos for housekeeping tasks.
- automatic updates of the database hosting the provenance files related to the model. More information in [Section 3.2.11](#).
- automatic notifications to the Inference Platform to update the deployed models endpoints. More information in [Section 3.2.4](#) (OSCAR).

[3.2.2 - New PAPI functionalities](#)

AI4EOSC Platform API (PAPI) [\[ai4-papi\]](#) continues to evolve in line with the platform development and the user feedback.

First, we will create endpoints to retrieve **statistics** that are relevant to the users. These include:

- *User-wise, and VO-wise statistics*: these are mainly statistics that show what is the historic resource usage of a user and the VO they belong to. The numbers are extracted from the daily accounting script that makes periodic snapshots of the cluster to be able to monitor the platform. [\[ai4-accounting\]](#)
- *Platform-wise statistics*: these are mainly statistics that depict the current status of the Nomad cluster (total resources, available resources, active datacenters, active nodes, etc.). The numbers are extracted by querying the Nomad API.

Second, we will adapt PAPI to be able to **deploy in a federated cluster** environment. The main change will be to account for the fact that now the endpoints to access jobs will be different depending on which cluster node the job ends up landing. So we will adapt the job's template to retrieve the proper endpoint, as well as filtering the nodes depending on the project the node is supporting (AI4EOSC or iImagine). Both the endpoint and the supported project are added to the node metadata when creating them with Ansible [\[ai4-ansible\]](#).

Third, we plan to add an optional **email notification** feature that will send an email to the user when their deployment is ready to be used. This will be especially

useful for GPU deployments that sometimes can remain queued for quite some time due to high GPU demand.

Fourth, we plan to make **improvements in the integration with Vault**, in particular add the ability to save ssh keys (to support the new version of Flower that will power the Federated Learning server) and add the ability to access the secrets from inside the deployment, like MLflow credentials for experiment tracking or the Jupyterlab password.

Finally we are going to explore additional features, such as the ability to shelve deployments (so that they do not consume resources) or better handle the Nomad deployments from former or inactive users.

In addition to what has been described in this section, many of the changes described in the following sections will involve modifications in PAPI. Please refer to those sections for a description of the changes.

[3.2.3 - External datasets and marketplace integrations](#)

To further improve usability of the AI4EOSC platform we are planning on the integration of external platforms. For this, we envision two possibilities.

First is to **integrate external datasets**. This means that when users create new deployments, they will be able to select a dataset that is hosted in an external repository. When the deployment is created, the dataset will be automatically downloaded into the user's personal space in the platform's storage [\[ai4-storage\]](#). This will provide the user with an environment where they can run an AI workflow on ready-to-use data. In a single click we will provide the resources, the code and the data.

Using the Datahugger tool [\[datahugger\]](#), we will start by integrating datasets from the following repositories: Zenodo [\[zenodo\]](#), figshare [\[figshare\]](#), Hugginsface [\[hugginsface\]](#), DRYAD [\[dryad\]](#), Open Science Framework [\[osf\]](#), and Mendeley Data [\[mendeley-data\]](#). In a second iteration, we will try to push the synergies between EU projects, exploring how to integrate with the BioImage archive [\[bioimage-archive\]](#), developed within the AI4Life [\[ai4life\]](#), or with the data hosted by the RAISE project [\[raise\]](#).

This integration will require adding the dataset download sidecar task in the Nomad job launched by PAPI and creating a configuration page in the Dashboard, where the users are able to include datasets to their deployments in a friendly and interactive manner. More information in [Section 3.2.8](#).

Secondly, we plan to explore the **integration of external marketplaces** of AI models. This will allow users to deploy models that were not originally developed for our platform and thus not have a DEEPaaS API interface.

As a first use case, we will explore the possibility to integrate the models from the BioImage Model Zoo [\[bioimage-zoo\]](#), also developed within the AI4Life EU project [\[ai4life\]](#). In the future, we could explore very popular AI model marketplaces like Huggingface.

This will require for each integration, a template model in ai4os-hub, that will handle the mapping of the model functionality from the original platform to AI4EOSC (e.g. integrate the models with the DEEPaaS API predict method, etc.).

[3.2.4 - Try endpoints](#)

We will allow users to try model inference in two different ways.

First, we will have some modules in the Dashboard permanently deployed in the **OSCAR** Inference Platform [\[ai4-inference\]](#). The code to deploy those services is available in GitHub [\[ai4-muo\]](#). This will enable users to access the module's functionality *instantly*. This will require that a button is created in the Dashboard, that will redirect the users to the proper OSCAR endpoint assigned to that module.

To make sure those modules are always up-to-date, every time the module is updated, the Jenkins pipeline will trigger the Inference Platform to pull the latest image of the module and restart the deployment (see [Section 3.2.1](#)).

But having every single module of the marketplace constantly deployed is very resource intensive. So to minimise the resource consumption, we will restrict those permanent deployments to the most popular modules. To address this for less popular ones we will offer a second "Try" method.

As an alternative "Try" method, we will allow users to make *temporary* deployments in **Nomad**. Being temporary, this will allow us to offer a "Try" endpoint for less popular modules, as it does not make sense to have them permanently deployed.

For both try methods, we plan to allow users to access the endpoints both through the DEEPaaS API [\[deepaas\]](#) and through a Gradio interface [\[gradio\]](#) (built on top of DEEPaaS).

The "Try" method that leverages Nomad will require the creation in PAPI of a new set of routes and the definition of the proper Nomad job. Regarding the Dashboard we will need a button that calls to those routes to create such jobs.

In principle, we plan to make the Nomad endpoint only available to users authenticated with EGI Check-In, though we will not require membership to our project VO, so that anyone can potentially try the modules. To avoid the impact on the users that are already training modules with the Nomad cluster, we will implement additional safeguards (like restricting "Try" endpoints during periods of high cluster load, limiting the number of "try" endpoints per user, etc.).

3.2.5 - Inference endpoints

We will allow users to deploy their models for inference in two different ways, to try to cover different use case requirements. These endpoints differ from the “Try” endpoints, as they are meant to be more production-oriented, allowing to scale up resources with the user’s need. This is why those endpoints are only going to be available for AI4EOSC users, as well as other supported projects (iMagine).

The main deployment method will be to deploy a model in the project’s **OSCAR** serverless inference platform [\[ai4-inference\]](#). The main benefit of this approach is the *scalability* of the inference jobs. When a user needs to perform a massive amount of inferences, the OSCAR cluster will be able to autoscale, deploying automatically multiple instances of the model to execute the predictions. And when no user jobs are queued, the resources are freed, thus avoiding consuming resources when idle ².

To make the deployment of the endpoint transparent to users, we will implement a single-click button in the Dashboard. This will trigger a call in PAPI, that will deploy an endpoint in the OSCAR inference platform. The list of endpoints created by the user will be listed in the Dashboard.

When the endpoint is deployed, users will be able to make HTTP requests to it with the inference arguments to use. To make auto-deployment of any AI4EOSC model possible in OSCAR, we will develop a generic bash script that will be run by OSCAR. The script will read the arguments of the HTTP request and will forward them to DEEPaaS (using the DEEPaaS CLI), which serves as a common interface to all marketplace models.

The second deployment method is meant to complement the first one. It will allow users to deploy an inference endpoint in the project’s **Nomad** cluster, the same one used for training. The main benefit of this approach is readiness, as once the endpoint is created, the model will be constantly loaded allowing users to make fast queries, at the price of constantly using resources. This can be useful for applications that are making predictions in stream, rather than in batches.

Again, to make the deployment transparent to users we will implement a single-click button in the Dashboard. This will trigger a call in PAPI that will deploy an endpoint in the Nomad cluster. The list of endpoints will be listed in the Dashboard, similar to the current training deployments list.

² In this case, idle deployments do not consume resources because they are not running any process, contrary to the “Try” endpoints where OSCAR endpoints are running permanently the DEEPaaS API and exposing the DEEPaaS Swagger UI.

When the endpoint is deployed, users will be able to make HTTP calls to it with the inference arguments to use or interact directly with the Swagger UI from DEEPaaS.

3.2.6 - AI4Compose implementation

The AI4Compose [\[ai4-compose\]](#) component is responsible for supporting Composite AI by allowing the workflow composition of multiple inference requests to different AI models. This component is based on visual flow programming tools to efficiently process input data through the models deployed as services in OSCAR clusters, and generate meaningful outputs.

As described in Deliverable D5.2 [\[D5.2\]](#), we have implemented AI4Compose by integrating two different tools for visual composition: Node-RED [\[nodered\]](#) and Elyra [\[elyra\]](#). Despite their unique functions and capabilities, both platforms share a common goal of leveraging composite AI tools, and both of them have been properly integrated into the AI4EOSC platform. While Node-RED instances are managed by FlowFuse [\[flowfuse\]](#); Elyra is offered through Jupyter Notebooks environments (like EGI Notebooks [\[egi-nb\]](#), where we have collaborated to integrate Elyra support).

Users can choose between these two tools to compose their pipelines based on their working environment needs and prior experience. In [Figure 2](#) you can see how the interaction between users and AI4Compose components is performed.

Figure 2: Dynamic view of the AI4Compose architecture.

As depicted in [Figure 2](#), both Node-RED and Elyra use custom OSCAR nodes from public repositories to interact with OSCAR Manager. We've developed some initial custom nodes to easily interact with OSCAR clusters by providing just essential details (endpoint, service name, and service token). These custom nodes are available in the GitHub repo and published on the Node-RED Library [\[ai4-compose\]](#).

Considering that the main components of AI4Compose are already implemented and ready to use, our implementation plan for the second half of the project is focused on developing new custom nodes. Specifically:

- **Additional nodes for the models in the AI4Compose marketplace**, as, for example, the Plants Species Classifier model that has its corresponding Node-RED and Elyra nodes [\[plant-compose\]](#). We will develop new nodes for the most used modules in the marketplace. This also involves the generation of documentation for new nodes and updating the current nodes if the AI models vary.
- **New nodes to facilitate the composition of the results**: we consider developing new custom nodes or subflows to facilitate the post-

processing phase, after obtaining predictions from the models. In order to generate meaningful outputs, post-processing steps may be applied to refine or interpret the results. This can include tasks such as thresholding, filtering, output formatting or any additional processing necessary to obtain the final desired output.

- **Develop new nodes for the use cases of the project:** use cases from WP6, external use cases coming from the open call or other collaborating projects such as iMagine, might have interest in offering their models through the visual composition tools. Even some use cases might need to compose their AI models to offer an enriched output. For those cases, we will work with them to develop new custom nodes to interact with their OSCAR services and trigger inference of their AI models.

Moreover, we will maintain the current FlowFuse instance up-to-date and available for all the users of the AI4EOSC platform. Finally, we will continue improving the current documentation of the AI4Compose component, as well as preparing new tutorials and demos to ease its usage, as ready-made patterns can enhance the development.

3.2.7 - New tools

CVAT for image labelling

The Computer Vision Annotation Tools (CVAT) [\[cvat\]](#) is an open-source tool for image and video annotation provided as a cloud or self-hosted application. It supports various image formats (backed by Pillow [\[pillow\]](#)) and video formats (backed by ffmpeg [\[ffmpeg\]](#)), as well as 3D data. CVAT offers a wide range of annotation tools enabling annotation of different shapes such as rectangles, polygons, polylines, skeletons or tagging and attribute annotation tools. CVAT has semi-automated and automated labelling features: interactors (e.g., Segment Anything Model), detectors (e.g., YOLO v5), trackers (e.g. TransT - Transformer Tracking).

Figure 3: CVAT labelling panel. Image extracted from [\[cvat\]](#).

Within the AI4EOSC context, CVAT will be forked from its original repository and adjusted to make it deployable in the Nomad [\[ai4-tools\]](#). The modifications include:

- Adding the ability to *specify custom ports* for different CVAT services (e.g., Identity and Access Management, Open Policy Agent, Postgres and in-memory Redis databases) in order to ensure visibility of the services and proper functionality of the annotation tool.
- Adding a *superuser creation command*, which takes into account repeated deployment occurring within Nomad.
- Adjusting the original Docker image to enable *mounting of the AI4EOSC storage* [\[ai4-storage\]](#) with rclone [\[rclone\]](#). The storage serves as both the annotation data source and persistence enabler between the application shutdowns.

CVAT is a complex tool that requires +15 containers to be deployed simultaneously. It will be translated into a Nomad job integrated in PAPI. Once the Nomad job is created, upgrades to new CVAT versions should require much less effort. This will allow users to go directly to the Dashboard to deploy their own CVAT instance. Therefore users will be able to isolate different projects and have custom resources deployed to accelerate CVAT (eg. GPUs for AI assisted labelling).

Apache Kafka for stream data processing

Apache Kafka [\[kafka\]](#) is an open-source publish-subscribe messaging system that ingests data from multiple sources and persists the messages for

outcoming purposes. In other words, Kafka is a streaming processing service that handles the messages exchanges between the data source and a final application. It is a fault-tolerant high-performing service, able to process more than 600k events per second with a single instance, ideal for use cases with massive data processing needs [maharjan2023].

Kafka uses a queuing system that persists the data on disk following a retention policy. In the publish-subscribe architecture model of Kafka, a cluster of Kafka is a set of machines called *brokers*. The producers send information to the broker, while the consumer reads information from the brokers. Events are organised in topics and consumers can subscribe to multiple topics when receiving the information. This is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Kafka workflow. Image extracted from [kafka-img].

We will use Apache Kafka to efficiently implement data streaming for use cases that will need it (e.g. use cases that need to publish a continuous video stream to YouTube where a video is AI segmented with YOLO on real time).

At the time of writing, the Kafka cluster follows a replicated 3-node architecture which can scale up based on the demand. Each Kafka broker is installed on top of virtual machines exposed externally behind a proxy. To allow the external access to each broker from the users, new hosts per instance are manually defined in the EGI Dynamic DNS under the "*.dev.ai4eosc.eu" domain.

The setup adds a security layer using the SASL_SSL protocol needed to authenticate (SASL) [sasl] and encrypt (SSL) [ssl] the communication between the brokers and the application. SASL supports a list of authentication mechanisms such as PLAIN, GSSAPI (Kerberos), LDAP or Oauthbearer. Currently, Kafka is running under development with the basic PLAIN SASL

mechanism where a tuple of username and password is manually created for each application. During the second part of the project, we will explore the Oauthbearer mechanism in order to integrate the Kafka authentication with the AI4EOSC AAI service.

Apart from the stream processing, with this service, we will be providing a data centralization mechanism where multiple AI applications from the ecosystem will be able to consume the same published data (one-to-many) or for an AI application to combine multiple datastreams in novel ways (many-to-one).

3.2.8 - Improved user centric Dashboard

In the AI4EOSC Dashboard we will add a new **Dashboard section**³, which shows the statistics of the user deployments as well as some cluster related statistics. This section is organised in four tabs, each of them dedicated to an specific topic:

1. The **Overview tab** shows the number of CPUs, RAM, disk and GPUs that are being used in the cluster compared to those that are free. It also displays some statistics about the user's usage of the platform, specifically the number of jobs that they are running, number of CPUs and GPUs used, frequency of the CPUs used and the amount of RAM and disk consumed (see [Figure 5](#) for details).
2. The **Datacenters tab** presents a map with all the datacenters that are part of the cluster. When the user clicks on the location of any of the centres, an information panel is displayed, showing its PUE, energy quality, number of jobs running, and the resources consumed (CPUs, GPUs, RAM and disk) (see [Figure 6](#) for details).
3. The **Graphs tab** displays graphs about the usage over time and the historical aggregate usage of the cluster. The first part shows a graphical representation of the temporal evolution of the number of running and queued deployments as well as the use of different computational resources. The second part shows a pie chart for each type of resource which compares the user's usage to the total AI4EOSC usage (see [Figure 7](#) for details).
4. The **Nodes tab** lists all the nodes of the cluster in two groups: those which have only CPUs, and those which also have GPUs. Pie graphs about the availability of its resources are displayed for each of them (see [Figure 8](#) for details).

³ To avoid name confusion with the new section, we are considering renaming the AI4EOSC Dashboard.

Figure 5: Overview tab in Dashboard section.

Figure 6: Datacenters tab in Dashboard section.

Additionally, we aim to **improve the metadata of the available modules** in the platform, so that users would be able to filter and navigate through them more easily. Related to this, it is also planned to **redesign the module detail interface** and include more action buttons, such as a “Try” module button with which users would be able to experiment with the modules before training them, among other functions (see [Section 3.2.4](#)).

Regarding deployments, we will incorporate incremental improvements like an automated **carbon footprint estimation** of each deployment, based on factors like the datacenter efficiency, the number of hours of usage, the resources of the deployment, etc.

Figure 7: Graphs tab in Dashboard section.

Figure 8: Nodes tab in Dashboard section.

Regarding tools, the Dashboard will continue to improve the interface of existing tools as well as adding new ones (eg. CVAT) (see [Section 3.2.7](#)).

We also plan to **integrate the Dashboard more closely with the storage**. Users will be able to automatically import their storage RCLONE credentials to the Dashboard, removing any manual step to access the storage from the deployments. By allowing the users to “sync” their Nextcloud, the Dashboard will receive a set of authorised credentials that will securely be stored in Vault and injected in the Nomad job configuration. In addition to this, users will be able to automatically download external datasets to their storage, either from Zenodo or from other supported platforms (e.g. Huggingface, Figshare, etc.) (see [Section 3.2.3](#)).

3.2.9 - Model and data versioning

The MLflow service to track experiments and version models is already running in production and serving users.

For the second part of the project we will consider **using the MLflow Model Registry for storing AI models** as artifacts, instead of saving to Nextcloud (the current option). This could enable an easier User Experience (UX) by avoiding context switching.

The MLflow Model Registry is a centralised repository within the MLflow framework designed to facilitate the management, versioning, and deployment of machine learning models. It provides a comprehensive set of features for tracking and organising different stages of a model's lifecycle, including development, staging (deprecated after version 2.9.0), production, and archival.

Users can register new models, update existing ones, and transition models through various stages with ease, by using model version tags and stages. In **Figure 9** we provide an example of how this is achieved on a custom football dataset.

Figure 9: MLflow Model Registry interface example, where a model artifact is registered with a specific version, description, tag and alias.

In addition to the work on the Model Registry, we will improve the MLflow UI integration with the AI4EOSC Dashboard using Vault to secure the MLflow user credentials. Securing the credentials in Vault will also enable better retrieval of the information when generating the provenance files (see **Section 3.2.11**).

3.2.10 - Drift monitoring tools

On the same basis as DevOps in software development, automation of drift detectors can be implemented by the use of popular CI/CD tools. By triggering drift detection checks before the release of new data, developers can take proactive measures to address issues.

Tools such as Data Version Control (DVC) [dvc] allow developers to link specific states of data to model repository commits, providing with this all the benefits of version control (tools such as triggers for pipelines) while storing the data in their cloud of preference.

The scheme in Figure 10 shows an example of how a user can implement such a pipeline which can automatically verify the release of new data by leveraging CI/CD runners and a computing platform. Users can apply this basic example to extend their pipeline with options such as automatic publishing of data (e.g. Zenodo).

Figure 10: Workflow to perform data drift detection in CI/CD pipelines.

To avoid deploying the drift detector in the CI/CD host machines, we will deploy it in the Platform’s Nomad (via PAPI) using Just-In-Time (JIT) deployments in GitHub Actions or Jenkins CI/CD system. This will offload these expensive operations outside the CI/CD host machines, allowing the use of GPUs, if needed.

To be able to deploy the drift detector in the computing platform, we need to authenticate against PAPI. However, the OIDC access tokens we commonly use have short lifespans, limiting their use in automated workflows. This can be overcome by using MyToken [mytoken], that offers a secure solution for long-term and repeated tasks. Figure 11 shows the workflow of getting a long-lived token that will enable CI/CD to deploy in the platform.

Figure 11: Workflow for getting long-lived tokens that will enable CI/CD to deploy in the platform.

In parallel to the implementation of this workflow using GitHub Actions, we will explore the possibility of implementing it in our Jenkins CI/CD system. For this we will need to replace JIT deployments, evaluating the following options:

- *Execution assigned by the platform.* The Nomad Jenkins plugin [\[jenkins-nomad\]](#) can be installed in Jenkins in order to deploy agents as containers by demand from the build node.
- *Execution assigned by the user.* The Swarm Jenkins plugin [\[jenkins-swarm\]](#) would allow users to attach a Jenkins agent running in a container from any platform a user might choose.

In addition to the deployment of CI/CD drift analysis, there is a new development service which aims to provide high **visibility on the evolution of such drifts** in data. Our drift monitoring service aims to provide users with a database where they can store and visualise the trend of statistical properties of their data (i.e. p-values for drift analysis).

Figure 12: Data drift evolution in a synthetic dataset using Frouros.

In Figure 12, Frouros [ai4-mlops] has been used to generate multiple p-values on different mock up data versions according to a date, then those values have been uploaded to the server in order to be displayed as a trend in order to highlight the moment where the statistical properties of the data are compromised. It is possible to observe an outlier when the data is not in line with the previous dataset configured for detection.

At the moment this service is in the development phase. It provides basic authentication with OIDC, backend API and secure connections (HTTPS) but still requires further development on the frontend visualisations, multitenancy for users, email alert system and database auto backup services, which are going to be implemented in the second phase of the project.

3.2.11 - Model provenance

For the second part of the project, we will develop and put into production all the different components used to track provenance information in the AI4EOSC platform.

Prov-fetcher

The prov-fetcher will be responsible for **extracting provenance information** from different components in the architecture. It will be implemented using modern Java (JDK 17) [java] and the Spring Boot library [spring-boot], which is used for dependency management and injection and for implementing a Command Line Interface. The component will be released in an executable JAR file.

At the moment, prov-fetcher is already compatible with the Jenkins and MLflow APIs. Due to its modular architecture, it will be extended to extract information from additional metadata sources like Nomad (via PAPI) as well as the new metadata version for the modules, described in [Section 3.2.1](#).

Prov-tracker

The prov-tracker will be responsible for **managing the provenance fragments** provided by prov-fetcher. To do so, a PostgreSQL database [[postgresql](#)] is used (relying on JSON columns) and a HTTP API exposes CRUD operations (implemented in Java using the Spring framework [[jooq](#)]). A JSON-schema is optionally used to verify the structural consistency of the metadata fragments to be ingested in the system [[json-schema](#)].

Prov-tracker will also implement the required W3C RML (RDF Mapping Language) [[w3c-rml](#)] rules to convert the raw provenance fragments (typically serialised in plain JSON documents) into RDF documents. To do so, the CARML library [[carmml](#)] is used. CARML is a RML engine implemented in Java. By using RML declarations, CARML transforms structured sources (e.g. JSON or CSV) to RDF documents, in accordance with the RML spec.

The prov-tracker will be able to chain all the metadata fragments obtaining a complete provenance document, to be exposed to the AI4EOSC platform through the aforementioned API.

Prov-viz

The prov-viz will enable an **interactive visualisation of the complete provenance graph**. This visualisation could be embedded in the AI4EOSC platform using a simple iframe. A detailed review of the JavaScript/TypeScript libraries for interactively displaying graphs is being performed. Those libraries with better integration with React are preferred.

In addition to the visualisation graph, more innovative ways of interacting with the provenance document are being explored. In particular, the use of Large Language Models (LLM) is being tested to enable questioning the provenance document using natural language. In this way, a user could extract information from the provenance document just by writing questions like “which was the dataset used to train this ML model?”. This functionality would be especially important for extracting information from very complex or detailed provenance chains that are difficult to represent and explore with visual methods.

As an initial exploration of this task, the LangChain library [[langchain](#)] is being used to implement Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) capabilities [[rag](#)] over an open LLM (e.g. Mistral).

3.2.12 - Model metadata tools

For the second part of the project, we intend to redesign and improve the module's metadata workflow.

For this, we will create a set of tools to handle the different processing needs regarding those metadata [\[ai4-metadata\]](#). These needs include metadata validation, metadata translation between formats (eg. JSON to YAML), metadata migration between versions (eg. AI4OSv1 to AI4OSv2), etc.

In addition to this, we plan to develop a set of tools for translating from (and to) other relevant metadata schemas, like the FAIR4ML Metadata Schema [\[fair4ml-schema\]](#), using crosswalks between different formats in an automated way via the definition of RML rulesets. In this regard, we plan to keep a set of RML rules so that these can be used and extended for metadata translation, not only in the AI4EOSC project, but at a broader scope. Also, we are exploring to exploit the FAIRCORE4EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) in order to facilitate the transformation of metadata from one schema to another via registered crosswalks,

The updated metadata schemas will allow for much richer user experience, allow for much more fine-grained searches in the Dashboard (cf. [Section 3.2.8](#)).

3.5 CHANGES FROM THE PREVIOUS ROADMAP

For context, we will briefly comment some of the changes with respect to the previous Roadmap for the AI4EOSC 2nd Release, outlined in Deliverable 5.1 [\[D5.1\]](#):

- **Improved WMS authentication:**

This bullet point in the original roadmap has been removed as we believe the current approach to WMS authentication fits the platform's needs. This can be reconsidered in the future, if needed.

- **Dashboard user centric tools:**

This bullet points has been broken in several points in the current roadmap, in particular: "Improved user centric tools", "New tools", "External integrations"

- **Automatic deployments to OSCAR:**

This bullet point has been integrated inside the current roadmap point "Inference endpoints"

4 - CONCLUSION

This document has started commenting on the completion status of the Roadmap for the first part of the project, as well as giving a brief overview of the architecture changes that have occurred since the project started.

Then, we have proceeded to describe an updated Implementation Plan for the second part of the project, both offering a Timeline overview and a Roadmap section where all the expected new features have been discussed in detail. We have concluded with a brief section commenting on how the new Roadmap differs from the one proposed at the beginning of the project.

The presented status of the platform components and our understanding of the required further developments and effort, makes us confident that this Roadmap will evolve all WP5 components to the expected maturity level by the end of the project.

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